

SITE SPHINX	DATE 5/III/81	AREA E	SQUARE R17	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top:	Bottom:
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter:		Width:	Length:	Depth:

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/	No./	B&W: Roll/	No./
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DRAWN	Area Plan:	Feature Plan:	Sections:
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: The packing blocks were again removed down to the bottom large blocks sitting on the bedrock ledge on which the large vertical in-set slabs rest which form the side of the paw (as reconstructed). The E section showing almost all packing blocks and little soil fill was drawn as part of 1:20 section 33 from paw to paw. The soil (tan clay but more sandy, brown w/ large-small limestone chips) was at the bottom of the W section against the bedrock undercurve into the recessed shaley band was dug into to trace the face of the bedrock laterally toward W. for a depth of about 50 cm from previous cut through this fill. The soil contained, again, few small blue frit particles, few small grey mud flecks. The recess side of the shaley bedrock began to

curve further inward (to S into paw) at a point about 70-75 cm from seam between the 2 large inset slabs as it would be measured from outside face (N side) of them. From here the space began too narrow to continue the probe. The furthest ~~to~~ inward the curve of the recess could be traced was an additional 25-30 cm from approx. line of inner recess as already exposed. This looked to be a natural (weathered?) undulation rather than a cut opening into this recessed bedrock side of the paw. The recess did not appear upward into the bulge N-ward of massive part (Bed 2ii; shaley unit - bed 2i) of the bedrock, as would seem to have been case if it was an artificial opening of any size cut into the paw here. The "corner" of it was rounded. But this conclusion is not certain.

Rather than being taken out of the opening caused by Q3 removal, the soil taken from this probe and chips were pushed back into it as refill. The packing slabs were replaced as to their original positions w/ some of the chips from the tan clay brown soil packing put back. Some of the sifted soil matrix from the original removal, was poured over the top - by now it contained contamination of match sticks, bits of paper, etc. having been in a pile beside the N forepaw for months.

NOTE: It seemed the blue fat particles come mostly from higher level in the packing when the soil is more waxy, fine, and reddish.